

**AN ANALYSIS OF TRANSLATION SHIFT IN ENGLISH- INDONESIAN ON
SETTING MENU OF OPERA MINI ON SAMSUNG GALAXY J5**

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ABSTRACT

This study deals with the category shift and the equivalence in the English – Indonesian settings menu of Opera Mini on Samsung Galaxy J5. This is aimed to describe the category shift and the degrees of meaning equivalence found in the setting menu of Opera Mini on Samsung Galaxy J5.

This study used descriptive qualitative design. In order to achieve the objectives of the research, the writer conducted the research by collecting, classifying, and analyzing the data. The source of the data is Opera mini on Samsung Galaxy J5, while the data are words or phrases in the English – Indonesian setting menu.

The result of this study are: (1) there are 27 cases of occurrences of category shift found in the English - Indonesian setting menu of Opera Mini on Samsung Galaxy J5. They are structure shift with 14 cases or about 51.85 %, unit shift with 7 cases or about 25.92 %, intra-system shift with 6 cases or about 22.22 %, and there is no class shift or 0 %. (2) the category shift can affect the degree of meaning equivalence become fully or partially equivalent. There are 26 cases of occurrences of degrees of meaning equivalence found in the English - Indonesian setting menu of Opera Mini. It divided into 4 types: complete meaning with 20 cases or about 76.92 %, increased meaning with 3 cases or about 11.53 %, decreased meaning with 2 cases or about 7.69 %, and diferent meaning are only 1 case or about 3.84 %, and there is no lost meaning or 0 %.

Key words: Category Shift, Equivalence, Opera Mini

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A. Introduction

Everyone needs a language to communicate with other people. There is not only one language, but many languages in the world that people use for polyglotism or multilingualism communication. Language is a bridge for communication amongst human in society. The human has an innate ability to acquire a language for communication. On the contrary, animals communicate without using language. Human communicates with others with verbal and non-verbal communication. Verbal communication is verbally spoken to other people using sounds, words, and languages in order to make other people received the information or message. Whereas non-verbal is the opposite, a communication using sign languages such as eye contact, touch, gesture, etc.

Because of many languages in this world, people want to understand the meaning of other languages. In this case, people need to study translation. Translation plays an important role in understanding the different language. J.C Catford (1965:20) states that translation is a replacement of textual material in Source Language (SL) by equivalent textual material in Target Language (TL). So, it means that translation is transferring the meaning of the text from one language to another language, equivalently without changing the meaning of source language.

In accordance with the translation above, the internet is popular media to be used in translation. Translation can't be separated from the internet. Because there are many bureaus of translation, machine translator can be found on the internet. In line with that, when we use the internet, we need a program namely web browser applications for accessing it.

There are many web browser applications. One of them is Opera Mini, the popular web browser program that is widely used by internet users. It is popular web browser program that is suitable to be used in Samsung Galaxy J5 version. The original version of

Opera Mini is in English. It is translated into many languages including Indonesian. Menu of Opera Mini in English have correspondence to the translation shift, especially category shift.

Translation shift is changing of form when it is translated from one language (SL) into another language (TL). Catford (1965:73) states “by shifts, we mean departures from formal correspondence in the process of going from the SL to the TL”. In short, it is some of the changes occur in translation. There are two many types of translation shift, one of them is the category shift. Catford (1965:80) in Hatim (2001:15) introduces the category shift into some of types: the structure shift, class shift, unit shift, and intra-system shift.

Translation shift commonly can be found in the literary works or novel. However, it also can be found in the menu of web browser applications. In this study, the writer wants to analyze the shift between English as the SL and Indonesian as the TL in the setting menu of Opera Mini. The translation shift that occurred in the data could be in form of words, phrases or clauses. For example, there are two parts in the unit shift; upward and downward unit shift.

Based on the explanation above, the writer is interested to analyze not only the unit shifts but also the structure shift, class shift and intra-system shift that are found in the English - Indonesian setting menu of Opera Mini. The writer is also interested to analyze its equivalence.

This study is expected to contribute theoretically and practically for those who interested in learning about translation shifts, especially in the category shift. Theoretically, the result of this study is expected to be useful as an additional reference for the next research in studying about translation shift, especially category shift and its equivalence. Practically, the result of this study can give the new knowledge for the researchers in extending knowledge about translation shift.

The scope of this study only focused on the category shift and degrees of meaning equivalence. There are many languages in the setting menu of Opera Mini. So, the limitation of this study is English and Indonesian setting menu of Opera Mini on Samsung J5 version.

B. Review of related literature

(1) Translation

Translation is a process of transferring the meaning of a text from one language into another language. There are many notions of translation that have been defined by experts. Newmark (1981:7) states that translation is a craft consisting in the attempt to replace a written message and/or statement in one language by the same message and/or statement in another language.

(2) Translation Process

Mildred L. Larson (1984:3) states that the purpose of translation is to transfer the meaning of the source language into receptor language or target language. The translation process can be seen as follows:

Picture 1: translation process by Mildred Larson(1984:4)

(3) Translation Shift

Translation shift is changing of form when the SL is translated into the TL. Catford (1965:73) states that shift means departures from formal correspondence in the process of going from the source language (SL) to the target language(TL).

Catford (1965:73) introduces the translation shifts into two major types: level shifts and category shifts. Then, category shift is divided into four types; structure shift, class shift, intra-system shift, and unit shift.

(3.1) Level Shift

Level shift means that the SL item at one linguistic level has a TL translation equivalent at a different level. It would be something which is a shift from grammar to lexis, and vice versa

(3.2) Category Shift

Catford (1965:75) stated that the category shift referred to the unbounded and rank-bounded translation. Unbounded translation means the equivalences in the SL and TL can move freely up and down the rank scale. Meanwhile, rank-bounded translation means that it is tied at scale-rank such as word-for-word, morpheme-for-morpheme equivalence, etc.

Catford (1965:76) divided into four types of category shift: structure shift, class shift, intra-system shift, and unit shift. They are explained as follows:

(3.2.1) Structure Shift

Structure shift is the shift that involves a change in grammatical structure between the SL and the TL.

(3.2.2) Class Shift

Class shift occurs when there is a change of word class from the SL into the TL.

(3.2.3) Unit Shift

Unit shift means the changes of rank. It departs from formal correspondence in which the translation equivalent of a unit at one rank in the SL is a unit at a different rank in the TL.

The rank refers to the linguistic unit. The hierarchy of linguistic units are started from the lowest or smallest into the highest unit:

Unit shift can be from low rank to high rank (upward) or high rank to low rank (downward).

(3.2.4) Intra-System Shift

Intra-system shift is changing on the system of a language in the SL and the TL.

(4) Equivalence in translation

Translation aims to convey the meaning of the SL into the TL, in order to achieve equivalence. Bell (1991:6) stated that texts in different languages can be equivalent to different degrees; fully or partially equivalent, in respect of different levels of presentation (equivalent in respect of context, of semantics, of grammar, of lexis, etc) and at different ranks (word-for-word, phrase-for-phrase, sentence-for-sentence).

In line with that, Asruddin B. Tou (n.d) states that degree of meaning equivalence divided into fully equivalent (or complete meaning) and partially equivalent (increased and decreased meaning). Meanwhile, non-equivalent divided into different meaning and no meaning.

(4.1) Fully equivalent (Bell,1991:6)

Fully equivalent or the complete meaning, it occurs when the transfer happens from the SL into the TL without addition and omission/deletion the information. In this case, the information of the SL is completely transferred into the TL, without any changes of meaning.

(4.2) Partially equivalent (Bell,1991:6)

Partially equivalent occurs when the meaning in the SL is fully not transferred in the TL. It involves the addition or omission of the message. Partially equivalent consists two parts: increased and decreased meaning.

(a) Increased meaning

Increased meaning or addition of the meaning occurs when some information content which is not found in the source language text, but the translator adds some information into the target language text. In this case, the information contained in the TL increased.

(b) Decreased meaning

Decreased meaning or omission of the meaning occurs when the translator omits some information which is found in the SL text so the information content of the TL decreases. The translator does not transfer completely the meaning of the original SL.

(4.3) Non-equivalent meaning

Non-equivalent meaning is the meaning of the translation which does not convey the meaning of the original writing. The target language does not contain a term that corresponds in meaning, either partially or inexactly, to the source language. it occurs when one or more of the vocabularies used are narrower in scope than the other

vocabularies. In this case, non-equivalence may be replaced by adopting a loan term. There are two types of non-equivalent:

(a) Different meaning

This occurs when the result of translation that contained information in the source language text changed by words that have a different meaning in the target language text.

(b) No meaning

No meaning occurs when the translators eliminate all the information found in the source language text. So, the target language text loses all the information content of the source language.

(5) Opera Mini

Opera mini is one of popular browser application used in the mobile device such as smartphone and tablet computer that developed by Opera software AS. Opera Mini is an application for accessing information on the internet. The original version is in English. It has been translated into many languages including Indonesian.

In this study, the writer focuses on the settings menu of Opera Mini. Opera Mini used English as its original language, but it also can change into Indonesian language. The language translation in Opera Mini is not manually translated by a human. But it was translated automatically by machine translation of Opera Mini. In this study, the writer analyzes the category shift found in the English settings menu as the SL and Indonesian settings menu as the TL.

(6) Samsung Galaxy J5

Samsung Galaxy J5 is one of the popular mobile phones from South Korean which is widely used by users in Indonesia. This phone has two built-in web browser applications, e.g., Google Chrome and Internet Explorer. Opera Mini is an additional web browser application that is installed on the Samsung Galaxy J5.

(7) Previous study

This research is not the first study that deals with translation, especially category shift. There are several previous studies that relate to this topic. They are required by the writer as reference, guidance, and comparison intended for the purpose of developing this research. Most of the previous studies concern on the translation shift of literary work (e.g., novel, movie texts, etc) and legal documents (e.g., ID card, passport, etc). But in this present study, the writer will analyze category shift on settings menu of a web browser application namely Opera Mini. These are following previous studies that analyzed category shift in passport (Hasanuddin:2016), a novel (Munawaroh:2017) and movie texts (Kantiastuti:2014).

C. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study applied the descriptive qualitative research since the qualitative approach is used to describe the result of the research, which the writer by collecting, classifying, analyzing and drawing the conclusion.

A browser application namely Opera Mini on Samsung Galaxy J5 that taken from internet is the source of data. The data is words and phrases in English settings menu of Opera Mini as the SL and Indonesian settings menu of Opera Mini as the TL.

The main instrument of this research is the writer himself which spent much time by reading, identifying, analyzing and interpreting the data. There are some steps in

collecting the data of this research, in order to analyze the translation shift in the English and Indonesian menu of Opera Mini.

D. FINDING AND DISCUSSIONS

(1) Finding

Table 4.1 Type of category shift found in the English-Indonesian setting menu of Opera Mini

Code	SL	TL	Type of CS			
			SS	CS	US	ISS
OP/SM/1	Signed in to Opera	Sudah masuk ke Opera			√	
OP/SM/3	App layout	Antarmuka aplikasi	√			
OP/SM/5	Start page content	Konten halaman awal	√			
OP/SM/6	New tabs	Tab baru	√			√
OP/SM/7	Clear browsing data	Hapus data penjelajahan	√			
OP/SM/8	Night mode	Tampilan malam	√			
OP/SM/9	Fullscreen	Satu layar penuh			√	
OP/SM/11	Set as a default browser	Jadikan sebagai browser utama	√			
OP/SM/12	Notifications	Notifikasi				√
OP/SM/13	Lock screen news	Berita layar penguncian	√			
OP/SM/14	Page layout	Tata letak halaman	√		√	
OP/SM/15	Data savings	Penghematan data	√			√
OP/SM/16	Downloads	Unduhan				√
OP/SM/17	Advanced	Lebih lanjut			√	
OP/SM/19	Frequently asked Questions	Pertanyaan paling sering diajukan	√		√	√
OP/SM/20	Report a problem	Laporkan masalah			√	√
OP/SM/22	Check for update	Periksa pembaruan			√	
OP/SM/23	End-user license Agreement	Perjanjian lisensi pengguna akhir	√			
OP/SM/24	Privacy statement	Pernyataan privasi	√			
OP/SM/25	Third party licenses	Lisensi-lisensi pihak ketiga	√			
OP/SM/26	Installation ID	ID instalasi	√			
Total (27)			14	0	7	6
Percentage (100%)			51.85	0	25.92	22.22

Based on the table above, the writer found 27 cases of category shift. It can be seen that the highest frequency is structure shift with 14 cases or about 51.85 % and the lowest one

is the class shift with no case or 0 %. While the unit shift is found 7 cases or about 25.92 %.

The last, intra-system shift is with 6 cases or about 22.22 %.

Table 4.2 Type of degree of meaning equivalence in the English-Indonesian setting menu of Opera Mini

Code	SL	TL	Meaning Equivalence					
			EM			NE		
			CM	IM	DM	Dif	L	
OP/SM/1	Signed in to Opera	Sudah masuk ke Opera		√				
OP/SM/2	General	Umum	√					
OP/SM/3	App layout	Antarmuka aplikasi				√		
OP/SM/4	Theme	Tema	√					
OP/SM/5	Start page content	Konten halaman awal	√					
OP/SM/6	New tabs	Tab baru	√					
OP/SM/7	Clear browsing data	Hapus data penjelajahan	√					
OP/SM/8	Night mode	Tampilan malam	√					
OP/SM/9	Fullscreen	Satu layar penuh		√				
OP/SM/10	Languange	Bahasa	√					
OP/SM/11	Set as a default browser	Jadikan sebagai browser utama	√					
OP/SM/12	Notifications	Notifikasi	√					
OP/SM/13	Lock screen news	Berita layar penguncian	√					
OP/SM/14	Page layout	Tata letak Halaman	√					
OP/SM/15	Data savings	Penghematan data	√					
OP/SM/16	Downloads	Unduhan	√					
OP/SM/17	Advanced	Lebih lanjut	√					
OP/SM/18	Help	Bantuan	√					
OP/SM/19	Frequently asked Questions	Pertanyaan paling sering diajukan		√				
OP/SM/20	Report a problem	Laporkan masalah			√			
OP/SM/21	About Opera Mini	Tentang Opera Mini	√					
OP/SM/22	Check for update	Periksa pembaruan			√			
OP/SM/23	End-user license agreement	Perjanjian lisensi pengguna akhir	√					
OP/SM/24	Privacy statement	Pernyataan privasi	√					
OP/SM/25	Third party licenses	Lisensi-lisensi pihak ketiga	√					
OP/SM/26	Installation ID	ID instalasi	√					
Total (26)			20	3	2	1	0	

Based on the data above, there is the upward unit shift from compound–word to phrase. It can be seen that the compound word **Fullscreen** is translated into Indonesian noun phrase *satu layar penuh*. Basically, the word **fullscreen** is the compound word from adjective (**full**) + noun (**screen**). While the noun phrase of TL *satu layar penuh* has a constitution of ‘kata bilangan’ or numeral (*satu*) + noun (*layar*) + adjective (*penuh*). This translation indicates that there is a movement of the unit shift from the lower rank (word) to higher rank (phrase).

Complete Meaning: Data OP/SM/5: SL: Start page content

TL: *Konten halaman awal*

The translation above is complete meaning. There is a structural shift in the data. By this shift, even the meaning in the SL is completely transferred. The noun phrase **start page content** is completely transferred into *konten halaman awal* with no addition or deletion of the information. Because the noun **content** literally means *konten* which adopted from the word content itself. Whereas two nouns **start** and **page** are also accurately translated into the nouns *halaman* and *awal*, with no addition or deletion of information.

Decreased Meaning: Data OP/SM/22: SL: Check for update

TL: *Periksa pembaruan*

The data above is partially equivalent. Because there is information that omits in the TL. Both of the data are imperative sentences without a subject. They function as an instruction for the user of Opera Mini. The understood subject of the sentence is you, which means the reader or users. Here, the English sentence **Check for update** should be translated into correct translation *periksa untuk pembaruan*. But the translator omits the word *untuk* to

make the meaning in TL simpler and clearer. So, the translation is categorized as decreased meaning.

Different Meaning: Data OP/SM/3: SL: App layout

TL: *Antarmuka aplikasi*

There is different meaning in translation. The writer found the different meaning occurred in translating for the SL noun **layout** becomes a noun *antarmuka* in the TL. In English, the noun **layout** means a design of the screen. While in KBBI, the noun *antarmuka* means the connection between two objects that allows the user to interact with the system. In translating **layout** into *antarmuka* is classified as non-equivalent meaning because the word **layout** can be translated into the word *tata letak* as in data 14 (**page layout** is translated into *tata letak halaman*) instead of non-equivalent meaning *antarmuka*. In other words, the noun *antarmuka* has literal meaning to the word **interface** in English. So, in this context, translating the noun **layout** into the noun *antarmuka* is translation using a non-related word.

E. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

(1) CONCLUSION

1. In this research, the writer uses theory of the category shift based on Catford's theory. Almost all of the types of category shift are used to translate settings menu of Opera Mini, except the class shift. From 26 data, there are 21 data that occurred the shifts and 5 data didn't occur any shift or no-shift. From 21 data, there are found 27 cases of category shift. There are 14 cases or about 51.85 % belongs to the structure shift, it involves changing the position head and modifier at the word group or phrase level...

2. Category shift can affect in the meaning equivalence. In other words, the category shift can affect the results of translation becomes fully equivalence, partially equivalence, or

even non-equivalence. It is because of grammatical and cultural differences between the SL and the TL, in order to achieve the natural and closest equivalence....

(2) Suggestions

1. To the students

In translating, a translator must maintain the originality of the meaning of the source language. So, the students who want to be a good translator needs to widen the knowledge about every term in the SL and the TL, in order to achieve an accurate translation...

2. To the other researchers

This study is probably the first research about the category shift in a browser application namely Opera Mini. Thus, it is necessary to do further research on topics regarding the category shift in ways that have not been discussed in this study...

3. To the English Department

Translation shift is widely used in translations. It is important to the students to have good knowledge about translation shift, especially category shift and its equivalence. Therefore, giving special subject about translation shift in lectures is very important so that students can understand and enrich their knowledge to get accurate and natural translation...

F. REFERENCES

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